

EARLY POSTOPERATIVE MORTALITY IN ANATOMIC AND ATYPICAL LIVER RESECTIONS**Dimitar Rusenov**

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Abstract

Liver surgery is historically one of the "youngest" areas in abdominal surgery, but he most technically challenging surgical procedure in due to the complex anatomical arrangement in the liver.

The development of new intraoperative techniques, as well as increased knowledge of the anatomy and pathophysiology of the liver after hepatectomy, have contributed to the reduction of postoperative complications.

Keywords: liver resections, complications after liver resections, postoperative mortality

Introduction:

Establishing a prognostic role of the type of liver resection for the risk of early postoperative mortality. Choice of liver resection method - anatomic or atypical.

Objective:

Determination of a possible prognostic role of the type of liver resection (anatomic or atypical) for the risk of occurrence, frequency and severity of postoperative specific complications-mortality.

Materials and methods:

For the period from January, 2007 - March, 2018 in Clinic of liver, biliary pancreatic and general surgery, Acibadem City Clinic Tokuda Hospital ,1021 interventions were performed on the liver:

Cases of intervention other than liver resection by definition were excluded ISGLS, "removal of part of the liver parenchyma due to involvement by a disease process or traumatic injury resulting in devitalization of the parenchyma".

Thus, the study did not find the cases of:

- hepatotomy;
- cystotomies and cyst resections, practically without removal of functioning or pathologically altered liver parenchyma;
-liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors. liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors;
- interruption of trunk branches of the hepatic artery and/or portal vein with the aim of hypoperfusion of a given area (segments, lobe);
- suture of the liver in trauma;
Thus, a total of 852 cases of liver resections were included in the series

Results:

Early postoperative mortality 19 fatal outcomes were found in the early postoperative period for the entire series (2.2% early postoperative mortality), without a statistically significant dependence on the type of procedure - Anatomic liver resection (2.1%) or Atypical resection (2.2%) in the entire series (Table 1)

Table 1

Mortality after Anatomic liver resection and Atypical

Exitus	Statistics	type of resection		Total
		Anatomic resection	Atypical resection	
No	N	224	610	834
	%	97,4%	97,9%	97,8%
Yes	N	6	13	19
	%	2.6%	2.2%	
Total	N	230	623	853
	%	100.0%	100.0%	

The main causes of early postoperative mortality:

A-specific post-resection complications

- Liver failure - 5 cases,
- Hepato-renal syndrome – 2 cases;
- Internal bilirubin, peritonitis, sepsis – 2 cases.

B– non-specific complications

- Cardiac - acute coronary event, rhythmic death, progressive heart failure, observed in 4 cases;

- Respiratory failure, BTE, Mendelssohn syndrome – 4 cases;

- Other - ischemic stroke (1 patient)

The analysis showed that early postoperative mortality after Anatomic resection was higher compared to Atypical liver resection and in multivisceral resections (3.5% vs. 3.0%, respectively) and as a stand-alone intervention (1.7% vs. 0.5%, respectively.) [1-15]. (Table 2)

Table 2

Postoperative mortality after Anatomic and Atypical resections performed alone or as an element of multivisceral resection

Another operation	Exitus	Statistics	Anatomic resection	Atypical resection	Total	P
No	No	N	114	218	332	0,276
		%	98,3%	99,5%	99,1%	
	Yes	N	2	1	3	
		%	1,7%	0,5%	0,9%	
Yes	No	N	110	392	502	0,761
		%	96,5%	97,0%	96,9%	
	Yes	N	4	12	16	
		%	3,5%	3,0%	3,1%	

Discussion:

Five of the observed patients developed acute liver failure, leading to a fatal outcome. Hemorrhage with tissue and organ hypoperfusion and liver hypoperfusion is a prerequisite for hepatocellular failure with a negative effect on the final outcome.

We recorded two other exits after internal bilirubin, peritonitis, sepsis.

The surgical technique itself must achieve:

- meticulous hemostasis of the resection surface
- minimized intraoperative blood loss,

Conclusion:

Liver resection surgery should be performed in centers with sufficient experience in this field, working according to established standards and algorithms, and also with well-developed interventional gastroenterology.

References

1. Birgin E, Tesfazgi W, Knoth M et al. Evaluation of the New ISGLS Definitions of Typical Posthepatectomy Complications. *Scand J Surg.* 2019;108(2):130-136
2. Birgin E, Tesfazgi W, Knoth M, Wilhelm TJ, Post S, Rückert F. Evaluation of the New ISGLS Definitions of Typical Posthepatectomy Complications. *Scand J Surg.* 2019;108(2):130-136.
3. Dimick JB, Pronovost PJ, Cowan JA, Lipsett PA. Postoperative complication rates after hepatic resection in Maryland hospitals. *Arch Surg.* 2003;138:41-46.
4. Disibio G, French SW. Metastatic patterns of cancers: results from a large autopsy study. *Arch Pathol Lab Med.* 2008;132(6):931-9.
5. Elias D , Cavalcanti de Albuquerque A , Eggenspieler P, et al Resection of liver metastases from a noncolorectal primary: indications and results based on 147 monocentric patients. *J Am Coll Surg.*1998;187(5):487-93.
6. Koch M, Garden OJ, Padbury R, et al. Bile

leakage after hepatobiliary and pancreatic surgery: a definition and grading of severity by the International Study Group of Liver Surgery. *Surgery.* 2011;149(5):680-8.

7. Laurent C , Rullier E , Feyler A , Masson B , Saric J. Resection of noncolorectal and nonneuroendocrine liver metastases: late metastases are the only chance of cure. 2001;25(12):1532-6.

8. Rahbari NN, Garden OJ, Padbury R et al. Post-hepatectomy haemorrhage: a definition and grading by the International Study Group of Liver Surgery (ISGLS) HPB (Oxford). Aug 2011; 13(8): 528-535.

9. Rahbari NN, Garden OJ, Padbury R et al. Posthepatectomy liver failure: a definition and grading by the International Study Group of Liver Surgery (ISGLS). *Surgery.* 2011; 149(5): 713-724

10. Starzl TE, Bell RH, Beart RW, Putman CW. Hepatic trisegmentectomy and other liver resections. *Surg. Gynec.*1975; 141, 429-37.

11. Rusenov. D. Comparative analysis of anatomic and atypical liver resections for occurrence of specific post-resection complications (biliraghia). – *Medical Review*, 56, 2020, No. 5, 25-28.

12. Rusenov. D. Post-resection liver failure-an early postoperative specific complication in anatomic and atypical liver resections.-*Medical magazine* 79, 2020, №79,60-63

13. Rusenov. D. Influence of clamping techniques in liver resections for the occurrence of specific post-resection complications- *Medical Review*, 56, 2020, No. 5, 29-32.

14. Rusenov.D Indications for liver resections in benign and malignant tumors. Literature review and own experience. – *Medical Review*, 57, 2021, No. 3, 46-56

15. Rusenov.D. Comparative analysis of anatomic and atypical liver resections for the occurrence of specific post-resection complications / early postoperative mortality /. – *Medical Review*, 56, 2020, No. 5, 29-32